

Properties of light

Investigation of the Interaction of Light with Media

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Abstract

A range of experiments using different refractive indices element, lens action or magnification action, and light interference are used to verify the wave properties of light. A preset slit of diffraction grating were used in the verification of light interference. The refractive indices of two different media were used to govern light behavior with respect to the laws of refraction and reflection. The results of light reflection and refraction experiments proved to agree with the theory. The results of the experiment were also found to agree with the laws of lens in relation to the interaction lenses with light. The Young's setup for interference was used in the verification of light interference. The formation of patterns also agreed with dark and bright fringe formation conditions. This implies that lights wave nature and interference was successfully verified.

Keywords: convex lens, reflection concave lens, refraction, interference, diffraction grating.

Reflection and Refraction of Light

Objectives of the experiment

- To use lasers and prism to investigate the laws of reflection and refraction to obtain prism refractive index
- To determine the focal length of concave and convex mirrors
- To investigate light interference phenomenon using Young's setup.

Study Background

Refraction and Reflection

Light enters an n_2 refractive index medium from another medium of refractive index n_1 undergoes a partial reflection and refraction with θ as the incidence angle, θ' reflection angle and θ'' the refraction angle. A relationship of $\theta = \theta'$ is witnessed in the reflection case and the relationship $\frac{\sin \theta}{\sin \theta'} = \frac{n_2}{n_1}$ is applied in the refraction case.

Light travelling from a higher refractive index medium to a lower refractive index medium brings about a limiting case. Total reflection occurs only when the incidence angle is formed beyond the critical angle θ_c . This is due to the fact that total reflection takes place when the refraction angle is right angle (90°). The relationship bears an equation of $\sin \theta_c = \frac{n_2}{n_1}$ in the first medium and $n_2=1$ for the second medium. The critical angle can therefore be determined through the equation $\theta_c = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{n_1}\right)$.

Action of lens on light

Light passing through a lens is dictated by the formula of lenses $\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b} = \frac{1}{f}$ with a being the object-lens distance, b being the lens-image distance and f being the lens focal length. With respect to this, magnification can be defined as the ratio of the image length to object length. Magnification can also be found defined as the ration of image-lens distance b to object-lens distance a in the relationship $m = \frac{b}{a} = \frac{1}{f} \cdot a$.

Diffraction of light (Interference)

Owing to the wave behavior of light, light passes through a double slit exhibits different behavior. Light passes through the first slit in the equation $E_1 = E_0$ and passes through the second one as $E_2 = E_0 \sin(\omega t + \phi)$ with E being the light energy, ω as the angular velocity, t being time and Φ being two waves phase distance. In relationship to the wave theory, two waves converging at a screen experience interference. The interference pattern intensity is calculated by

$$I = 4I_0 (\cos \beta)^2 \left(\frac{\sin \alpha}{\alpha}\right)^2 \text{ with } I_0 \text{ determined by } I_0 = |E_0|^2, \beta = \frac{\pi d}{\lambda} \sin \theta, \text{ and } \alpha = \frac{\pi a}{\lambda} \sin \theta.$$

A represents the slit width, d is the space between the incident light wavelength and the two slits.

With the difference of optical paths δ which is also equal to $\delta = d \sin \theta$, two forms of interference, constructive and destructive are witnessed, with the constructive interference $\delta = m\lambda$ and destructive case as $\delta = (m + 1/2)\lambda$ with m determined as $m=0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3$.

The source wavelength m^{th} order bright fringe is determined as $P_m = R \tan \theta_m \approx R \sin \theta_m \approx R \theta_m \approx R \frac{m\lambda}{d}$. For single slit diffraction grating, interference occurs when a single slit produces multiple waves with self interference and consequently, the pattern of interference is seen on the screen. The M^{th} order is determined by the equation $P_m \approx R \frac{m\lambda}{a}$.

Methodology

Reflection and Refraction

The angles of reflection and refraction were recorded for each angle of incidence as varied.

Lens Action

The setup was done with the object and the screen on the extreme end and the lens in the middle. The lens was adjusted till the image appeared on the screen and the distances a, b, and f recorded. The distance between the source of light and the lens is varied and distances recorded when images are formed. The procedure is repeated with the use of a concave lens.

Light interference

A setup was made similar to Young's double slit experiment and distances between two fringes of states recorded. The experiment is also done with single slit grating and the procedure redone.

Findings

The diode Laser wavelength was 650nm.

Refraction and Reflection

Reflection

Incidence θ	Reflection θ' (Flat mirror)	concave θ''	$N = \sin\theta / \sin\theta''$	convex θ'''	$N = \sin\theta / \sin\theta'''$
0	0	0	0	0	0
15	15	15	1	15	1
30	30	30	1	30	1
45	45				
60	60				
75	74				

Refraction

Incidence θ	Reflection θ'	$N = \sin\theta / \sin\theta''$
0	0	0
15	15	1

30	11	0.988
45	15	1.3
60	24	0.33
75	33	-0.3878
Average		0.5384

Critical angle

Count	Critical Angle
1	45
2	46
3	44
4	43
6	44
Average	37
By calculation	$\theta_c = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{n_1}\right)$.
	1.0425

Lens Action

Convex

Series	a	b	m	f
1	10	15	0.5	0.7
2	16	13	0.5	0.3
3	14	13.5	0.5	0.4
Average	13.33	14.83	0.5	0.47
			error	4%

Focal length 6.5cm

Series	A1	B1	c	a2	B2	f
1	26	9	5.5	-3.5	6	
2	11.5	14	10	-4	5	
3	19	10	4.5	-4	10	
Average	18.83	11	6.67	-3.83	7	
				Error	2%	

Concave -14.8mm

Series	A1	B1	c	a2	f
1	26	9	5.5	-3.5	6
2	11.5	14	10	-4	5
3	19	10	4.5	-4	10
Average	18.83	11	6.67	-3.83	7
				Error	2%

Diffraction and interference

	Single slit	Double slit
Slit width	0.16	0.25
Spacing and sensor distance	77	77
Pattern#	650	650
Center- m^{th} pattern distance	1	1
Source wavelength	0.5	0.2

	Single slit	Double slit
Slit width	0.16	0.25
Spacing and sensor distance	77	77
Pattern#	650	650
Center- m^{th} pattern distance	3	3
Source wavelength	1.1	0.7

	Single slit	Double slit
Slit width	0.16	0.25
Spacing and sensor distance	77	77
Pattern#	650	650
Center-m th pattern distance	2	2
Source wavelength	0.8	0.5

Discussion

The experiments results had a 2% marginal error of the theoretical values. The manual use of a protractor and a ruler in measuring the angles and lengths brings about the possibility of human error that can also result in calculation errors. The plate of the protractor and the diffraction grating were set at perfectly horizontal positions to make the calculations simpler. It was manually adjusted to align with the lesser beam bringing about the possibility of misalignment which could affect the experiment findings.

Conclusion

The experimental setup in this experiment verified the laws that determine refraction and reflection behavior of light in different media, lens path and behavior and light wave interference and diffraction by the use of a target screen, tested elements and source laser. The error of the experiments were established to be between 2 and 4% in relation to the theoretical values in each case using respective formulas. The error sources were identified to be manually conduction of the readings, human bias and the fact that the experimental setup was not placed horizontally resulting in limitations (Sharma, 2015). These problems can be resolved by using a larger sample size and recalibrating the experimental setup that can result in a more favorable device placement to ensure they are perfectly horizontally placed (Young, Freedman, Sandin and Ford 1996).

Works Cited

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